

TOXIC OF EFFECT HIGH NICKEL INTAKE ON THE HUMAN BODY AND REMOVAL FROM WATER BY LOW COST ADSORBENTS

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INTRODUCTION

Table 1 Nickel in groundwater of industrial area of India The industrial town of Kanpur has a many cotton textiles , chrome leather tanning , chemical manufacturing industries . A survey was conducted and found that in comparison to other industrial areas of India the ground water of kanpur city contains a very high concentration Ni Table 3. [Ground Water Quality Series 1996-97] Table 2 Nickel status in soils of Haryana state India Table 4 effect of Nickel [20-80mg/kg] contaminated soil on plant growth [Hisar . Haryana]

TABLE 1 NICKEL IN THE GROUNDWATER OF INDUSTRIAL AREAS OF INDIA

Area	mg /l	Industry
Rourkela ,Bihar	0.0 - 0.66	steel
Goa	0.10- 0.34	ore-mining
Himachal Pradesh	0.013-0.14	
Uttar Pradesh	0.01-0.033	“ “
Kerala	0.002-0.004	“ “

TABLE 2 NICKEL STATUS IN SOILS OF HARYANA STATE

Range of Ni mg/kg	Total area km 2	% Area
< 0.75	25083.83	56.79
0.75- 1.25	8837.0	20.00
1.25-1.75	5711.1	12.93
1.75-2.25	2596.3	05.88
>2.25	1940.3	04.39

TABLE 3 NICKEL IN GROUNDWATER OF INDUSTRIAL AREA OF KANPUR CITY .UP .INDIA

block		
JAJMAU	KA1	0.05
	KA2	0.04
	KA3	0.05
	KA4	0.05
PANKI	KB1	0.09
	KB2	0.04
	KB3	0.05
	KB4	0.07
	KB5	0.04
	KB6	0.04
NARAIKHEDA	KC1	0.04
	KC2	0.03
	KC3	0.06
	KC4	0.09
	KC5	0.06
	KC6	0.16
RAKHIMANDI	KD1	0.09
	KD2	0.09
	KD3	0.11
	KD4	0.09
	KD5	0.11
	KD6	0.06

TABLE 4EFFECT OF NICKEL [20- 80mg/kg] CONTAMINATED SOIL ON GROWTH [HISAR . HARYANA]

Crops	% age reduction
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Brassica juncia	19.70
Brassicacarinata	19.40
Green gram	5.0
Pegion pea	12.0
Black gram	20.8
Wheat grain	37.4
Barley grain	5.30

HEALTH HAZARDS DUE TO HIGH NICKEL INTAKE-

Heavy metals Ni, As, Hg, Pb, Cd act as effective enzymes inhibitors. The viruses or carcinogenic metals with their tendency for chelation are associated with vitamins; protein and nucleic acid. These metal ions may replace the (ZnII, MgII) from the normal enzyme system or nucleic acid and may alter the structure and function of genetic material resulting in the formation of cancer. It has been shown that specific metals are required for genetic regulation and wrong metal ions, even the essential metal ions in wrong concentrations can lead to errors resulting in metal carcinogenesis. The fashioned DNA molecule requires only deoxy nucleotides and not ribonucleotide be incorporated into the nucleic acid. The ability of DNA polymerase I to distinguish between these two monomer types has been shown to depend on the nature of the metals used to activate the enzyme thus the presence of Mg(II) insure incorporation of deoxynucleotides, but Ni (II), Mn(II) and Cr(VI) permits the concurrent incorporation of ribonucleotides. Thus the presence of Ni (II), Mn(II) and Cr(VI) lead to incorporation of the wrong sugar (Ribonucleotides) in place of deoxynucleotides into the nucleic acid with both type of enzyme (RNA and DNA polymerase) carcinogenic metals are supposed to cause error. [Chakrawarti.2003]

METHOD AND MATERIALS Preparation of adsorbents

For manganese dioxide impregnation, the reported method [KiranKumar1984] was used. Crushed and washed coal having geometric mean size 0.102 mm (24g) was added to a solution of potassium permanganate (26.675 g in 325 ml distilled water) at 90 C in a water bath. The slurry was stirred for 10 minutes, followed by slow addition of 300 ml of 2 N hydrochloric acid in 10 minutes with constant stirring. Stirring was continued for another 10 minutes followed by washing of excess precipitate

with distilled water and 0.05 M perchloric acid till the supernatant liquor becomes clear. The adsorbent following pretreatment / impregnation was removed, washed several times with distilled water, dried at 60 + 1 C and desiccated. Iron (III)hydroxide impregnation on coal was done by reported method [Jyotsna Lal 1992] Crushed and washed coal having geometric mean size 0.102 mm (20g) was slurried in 100ml distilled water to which 2gm of iron(III)chloride was added Using 2 N sodium hydroxide solution the pH of the slurry was then adjusted to ~11.5 and the total volume made upto 200ml ,the slurry was allowed to settle for 24 hr. The adsorbent following pretreatment / impregnation was removed, washed several times with distilled water, dried at 60 + 1 C and desiccated. All solutions were prepared using analytical grade chemicals . Stock nickel solutions were prepared from nickel sulphate .Batch adsorption studies were carried out in stoppered conical flasks using a mechanical shaker. pH was adjusted by a digital pH meter. nickel was analysed in solution using EDTA complexometric titration and spectrophotometrically

FIGURE 4 Ni[II] REMOVAL BY IRON HEXAMINE MODIFIED SAWDUST

FIGURE 5 Ni[II] REMOVAL BY ACTIVATED CARBON FROM SAWDUST

FIGURE 6 REMOVAL OF Ni [II] BY AQUATIC PLANTS SALVINIA MOLESTA AND SPIRODELA POLYRHIZA

FIGURE 8 Ni[II] REMOVAL BY WATER LETTUCE , PISTIA STRATIOTES

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Low cost adsorbents [CMnO₂] manganese dioxide Figure 1 and [CFe]Iron (III)hydroxide impregnated coal Figure 2 tested for Ni [II] removal from water were found good adsorbents removed 99.79mg /gm 151.4 mg /gm respectively

Na₂CO₃ treated ricehusk was in a column ,bed depth of 30cm loaded Ni 20mg per litre showed 100% removal at flowrate 11ml per minute in 7-8 hrs at pH~6-7 [Figure 3]

Activated carbon from sawdust [Figure 4]nickel removal 40 mg /100 mg AC increases with pH in the range 7-10 the maximum adsorption observed might be due to partial hydrolysis of metal ion due formation of MOH⁺ and M[OH]₂ low solubilities of the hydrolysed metal ion species may be the reason for maximum adsorption in this pH range

Ironhexamine treated sawdust [Figure5] here the uptake of Ni decreases with increase in acidity of the solution 20gm Ni per gm MSD

Figure 6 the aquatic plants *Salvinia molesta* [mitch] and *Spirodela polyrhiza* [schleid] were grown in metal enriched solution ,the specific growth rate 0.1-0.35g/day each fond absorbs metal ions from the water through the entire plant and not through the a central root system .The plants were weighed after 14 days and analysed for metal ions both plants survived upto 25ppm

Salvinia molesta is more effective than *Spirodela polyrhiza* removes 78% from 4ppm feed solution in a period 2-6 days ,the uptake decreases to 70% in 14 days as plants become saturated *Spirodela polyrhiza* 55% in 2-6 days which decreases to 30% in 14 days Hence *Salvinia molesta* has higher metal concentration factor . while biomass growth decreases at

8ppm The percentage removal of Ni by leaf powder of *Tephrosia Purpurea* at lower dosage 1.5gm of leaf 58% at 4.5 gm 92.86% at 50 ppm at 40 rpm and time 60 minutes

ni [II] removal from water was done by aquatic plants uptake of Ni upto 5.32 and 7.85 mg/gm dry plant tissue of water hyacinth and water lettuce respectively Figure 7.8water lettuce is a better option for nickel than water hyacinth

TABLE 6 MICROORGANISMS WHICH CAN BIND NICKEL IN THEIR BIOMASS

Microorganism		Site of binding
Candida sp	Ni	cell wall [mannan-protein layer & inner glucan -chitin layer]
Cyano bacteria	“ “	
Anabena ,Nostoc sp		
Arthro bacter ,Klebsilla		
Consortia of bacteria , Staphylococcus aureous		
Bacillus lichencforms	Ni , Cu, Fe [III] , Mn , Au .	Cell wall [Teichoic acids
Bacillus subtilus	Ni Fe ,Mn ,Cu , Zn , Mg , Pb	Cell wall [Peptidoglyan]

Metal accumulation by micro organisms environmental scientists and engineers try to utilize this property of bio accumulation for monitoring metal pollution as well as removal \ recovery of property of bio accumulation for metals from natural and waste waters . table 6 microorganisms which can bind nickel in their biomass

Use of adsorbents derived from plant biomass sawdust , rice husk, tealeaves are cheap and effective similarly coal based adsorbent CFe and CMnO₂ can be used for nickel though the kinetics need to be studied . Phytoremediation of nickel by *Salvinia molesta*, *Spirodela polyrhiza* ,*Eichhornia crassipes* and water lettuce from water offer good alternatives.

REFERENCES

- R.K.Srivastava, S.K.Gupta [1993] Treatment of chromium and nickel in waste water
By using aquatic plants *Water Research* ,43, 1631-1637
- D,K. Singh ; N.K Mishra [1992] Removal of toxic heavy metals ion using modified
Adsorbents *Pollution Research* 11187-190
- K.Kadirvelu; V.Subburam [2003] Activated carbon prepared from biomass as an adsorbentFor Ni[II] removal
IJEP 23 1343-1349
- G.Donmen.Aksu[2001]Bioaccumulation of copper [II] and nickel [II] by non adapted and
Adapted growing candida *Water Research* 35 ,1425-1433
- V.M.Murali Ksai [2001] Some studies on adsorption of nickel by *Tephrosia Purpurea*
IJEP 21,1073-1074
- A.K Panda[1996]Bioaccumulation of nickel and zinc by water hyacinth

Ind.J Environ .Hlth,38,51-53

Upendra and Manas Bandhopadhyay[2005] Fixed bed column study for from aqueous waste By NCRP Research Journal of chemistry and Environment ,9, 83- 86

Vogel 1978 Textbook of quantitative inorganic analysis English language book society EL BS London

Jyotsna Lal; DK Singh;[1992] Removal of toxic metal ions from waste water by coal based adsorbent , Pollution Research,11,37-42

Kiran Kumar .T.V[1994] Manganese dioxide impregnated bituminous coal,M.Tech.Dissertation I.I.T.Kanpur

Kamble.KS;Patil,M.R[2001]Removal of heavy metals from wastewater of thermal power station by water hyacinths IJEP, 21,623-626

A.K Sen..and A.K De. [1987] Adsorption of mercury II by coal fly ash , Water Research ,21, 885-888